

INTERLINGUISTIC LANGUAGE RELATIONS

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Abstract: *Language is the greatest national value. Language is not just a means of communication, perhaps, as a product of thought, it is also the basis for creating innovation. Language, along with the function of communication in society, affects and accumulates emotions. It also fulfills its functions. The social significance of language in the process of globalization. The feature is expanding. Language and society, language and thinking, language and analysis of speech relations, formation and development of languages development, history of writing, significance, origin and development of language development, description and classification of world languages, basic aspects of linguistics the study of concepts and methods of analysis knowledge of the nature of language, the product of its development it serves to develop skills and abilities.*

Key Words: *Linguistics, morphological, syntactic, lexical-semantic, stylistic, language and society, language and thought, language and culture, language and psychology, language and semiotics.*

Scientific paradigm (from Greek "example, model") is a set of specific, interconnected research methods aimed at studying the object of science and its theoretical concepts that prevailed in a certain period, and on this basis are similar in different branches of science. This term was introduced in 1962 by the American philosopher and historian T. Kuhn in his famous work "The Structure of Scientific Revolutions" ("Структура научных революций"; translated into Russian in 1977).

According to T. Kuhn, "paradigm is a set of distinctive methods and approaches used by certain scientific or philosophical communities united by common scientific and philosophical ideas, having their own research activity and object." Paradigmatics is an aspect of examining language units as elements of paradigms belonging to the language system. Paradigmatic relationship is the interaction of language units uniting into a single paradigm. Paradigmatic relations occur between words belonging to the same part of speech and having some commonality in meaning. Paradigmatics is an aspect of examining language units as an element of paradigms belonging to the language system. Paradigmatic Units included in such a set of words 112 Paradigmatic relations belong to one part of speech can be used interchangeably in the same positions within a sentence. Paradigmatic and

syntagmatic relations are included in such a set of words closely interconnected with the semantic features of lexical units.

Paradigmatic relations serve as the basis for dividing words into semantic classes. The functions performed by units of the same paradigmatic class within a sentence are similar to each other. Paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations interconnected with the semantic features of lexical units connected. Paradigmatic relations between words and semantic classes serves as the basis for division. The functions performed by units of the same paradigmatic class within a sentence are similar.

Paradigmatic series are united on the basis of a certain common feature, contrasting with some distinctive (specific) feature and alternating one with the other according to the requirements of speech communication units (elements). F. de Saussure's relationship between linguistic units his serious attention is clearly evident both in defining the concept of value and in defining the systemic nature of language. His according to him, in a certain period of language, everything depends on relationships is justified. The set of stable (ubiquitous) relationships constitutes language and determines its functioning. Therefore, the system's each member is determined by its syntagmatic and associative relationship with other members. F. de Saussure on the nature of relations divides into two groups: a) syntagmatic relations; b) associative relations attitude. These two attitudes relate to two forms of our mental activity corresponds to.

The interaction of units of linguistic levels in the speech of the language the main factor ensuring the fulfillment of the communicative task is dates. Therefore, in this case, paradigmatic, syntagmatic units of language and speech and the issue of hierarchical connection is a priority This is natural. This connection, in turn, is complex in nature. Indeed, paradigmatic relations are distinguished from syntagmatic relations, while syntagmatic relations are distinguished from hierarchical relations hard to imagine. Because members of certain paradigms interact with each other syntagmatic relation within the framework, a hierarchical relationship is formed. The syntagmatic connection of any level units occurs within a level that is one level above the level to which they belong. In addition, within the framework of the syntagmatic relationship, there is also a specific paradigmatic relationship will occur. We see evidence of this in syntactic paradigms.

A phoneme's ability to distinguish between a morpheme or a word's sound shell is not just a phonetic change. In this process, the phoneme exhibits its differential features. Of course, this characteristic plays an important role in the emergence of the

phonological phenomenon that is called an internal hierarchical relationship in modern linguistics. In other words, this kind of differential feature serves as the basis for the formation of a micro-level called the merismatic level. In other words, this kind of differential within the phonemic level. A phoneme's differential features cannot form segments. However, it is distinguished by the fact that it necessitates the internal division of the phoneme. The differential (merismatic) features of phonemes constitute the lower level (subphonemic) within the phonemic. Therefore, at the same time, a hierarchical relationship is formed between the elements of the phonemic and subphonemic levels. Merismatic level units (more precisely, elements), unlike the units of the phonemic level, therefore, at the same time, phonetic and lower phonemic cannot enter into syntagmatic relationships. Only paradigmatic relationships are formed between them. Therefore, some linguists argue that merisms cannot constitute a separate level. For example, V.M. Solntsev states that because merisms Only a paradigmatic relationship is formed between them. Cannot enter into syntagmatic relationships, they do not meet the condition of language levels "consists of..." and "belongs to..." For example, the merisms of V.M. Solntsev and therefore it is incorrect to interpret them as a separate. In our opinion, V.M. Solntsev's statement is close to the truth. Therefore, in linguistics literature, the concept of "subphonemic level" is used in this context. It should also be noted that phonemes are in a paradigmatic relationship only within the framework of the phonemic level. In units of levels higher than the phonemic level, they constitute the signifier aspect of the sign and enter into syntagmatic relationships with each other. However, the relationship between levels cannot acquire this characteristic. Because they are surrounded by a hierarchical relationship. Therefore, the relationship between the phonemic level and the morphemic level, the morphemic level and the word level, etc. Indeed, every theory that exists in linguistics is, first and foremost, based on how language is understood. How language is understood is important in creating a theory about language. The object of linguistics, its subject matter, and methods of scientific language study are to some extent related to how language is understood. In the history of linguistics, different definitions of language led to different conceptions of the subject of the science. Therefore, it is advisable to examine how this issue was addressed at the main stages of the history of linguistics.

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